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“TURNING PAGES, LIFTING CAPS”

Four years pass and go like turned pages.

With each chapter, there was wisdom.

Lectures and books, obstacles overcome,
dreams chased with fervent haste.

Early mornings, late nights,
heartaches, laughter, and moments shared given.

Now tassels turn, and caps are lifted high,
a dream realized in skyward illumination.

Though futures yet are still unclear,
we move with courage, not with fear.

More than parchment on our hands.

We bear the strength to rise.

We've acquired voice, bond, and name.

And moments past to time.

With minds conjoined and hearts upheld,
steadfast as one, we rise and soar.